

Layers of Meaning: Co-Designing with Bilingual Youth to Unearth their Reading Practices

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ABSTRACT

This paper examines migration and belonging through the lens of heritage language and young people's engagement with reading for pleasure. We argue that a better understanding of multilingual youths' engagement with reading can help libraries devise better ways of supporting their intertwined identities as members of linguistic, cultural, and reading communities. This study presents the theoretical framework and research design for an ongoing study of Canadian youth in Ontario (aged between 13-18, and members of the French official language minority community) along with their engagement with reading (not limited to print texts and books alone). A co-design approach was selected to engage youth in exploring their relationship to reading, identity, and libraries. Data collection is currently underway and involves pre- and post-surveys of youth, workshop materials and fieldnotes, a reading diary activity, and interviews with school and public librarians. An interpretive lens will be essential to making sense of the rich data stemming from a range of artifacts collected and analyzed.

KEYWORDS

Francophone youth, Reading, Co-Design, Heritage Language, Collaborative Interpretation

INTRODUCTION

As a multicultural and multilingual society, Canada has long prided itself for being an inclusive society, with urban centres as the focal points for that diversity. Libraries, archives, and museums (LAMs) play a crucial role in communities as spaces of gatherings, learning, memory, and culture, and yet collections and programming in Canadian LAMs (outside Quebec) are oriented primarily toward English-language patrons and decoupled from the complex multicultural and multilingual backgrounds that many Canadians have (Ghaddar & Caidi, 2014; Nomura et al., 2013). That same standard of exclusion also applies to French language despite official Canadian bilingualism. Francophones (broadly defined to include French speakers and French learners) in Canada and in Ontario are a very diverse community, with a large proportion in recent years hailing from the global diaspora (CSLF, 2018). Globally, French is the 4th language most used on the Internet and is in the top 5 languages most spoken in the world, with 321M French speakers, and an increase of 15% of speakers in Sub-Saharan Africa where many youths are still schooled in French (OIF, 2022). In Ontario, this reality is also reshaping the francophone landscape and the nature of young people's engagement with LAMs as members of official language minority communities (OLMCs).

This study investigates the following research questions: 1) What does reading mean to francophone youth in Ontario? 2) To what extent does youths' engagement with reading in French relate to their other practices and social interactions online and offline? 3) How can libraries best support the reading needs and practices of bilingual youth? The goal is to generate a theoretical model about how to better understand multilingual youths' engagement with reading and produce recommendations for practicing librarians (and other stakeholders) in devising better ways of supporting the youths' intertwined identities as members of linguistic, cultural, and reading communities.

In the context of this project, we interpret reading as engagement with stories, not engagement with published texts alone (Dali & Hohmann, 2022); hence, an expanded and inclusive definition of reading will guide this project and determine engagement with different formats including digital content, oral traditions, etc. As part of the data collection, we will collect a range of artifacts (DIY videos, video and audio recordings of the workshops, data from the online reading diaries, collaborative usability assessment by youth of the Francophone section of library websites, to name a few) and negotiate the terms of engagement with these data. A collaborative interpretation lens and approach will be critical to the success of this project. Our aim is to learn from colleagues at the ASIS&T Workshop about strategies and lessons learnt.

METHODOLOGY

Studying the reading practices and literacies of youth using co-design and participatory methods helps researchers better understand their lived experiences, and how these experiences are reflected in their reading practices. Furthermore, these types of studies provide an opportunity for youth to self-reflect and better understand themselves through their own reading identities (Ybarra, 2022). To investigate the phenomenon under study, primary data gathering consists of three separate parts: two (2) one-day workshop with youth, a diary activity/journaling process completed over two months by the youth, and semi-structured interviews with public and school librarians. As this project is focusing on youth, the age range for the participants is 13 to 18 years old, which corresponds to the critical shift from elementary to middle or high school, and, in some cases, new forms of socialization for the youth. The participants need to self-identify as either Francophone, French-speaking, or French learners and as avid readers. Recruitment into the program is underway and was done through several venues and targeted the broadest possible community of 13 to 18-year-olds in Ontario, both in the school system and outside of the school system. In total, 15 youths are currently participating in the program. Consent from both the participants and their parents/legal guardians were obtained for each part of the study.

The co-design workshops (which include a pre- and post-survey of the youth) take place in two different sites in order to attract youth from diverse backgrounds and lived experiences within the francophone community, and consisted of various activities with the overarching aim being to discuss how the youth viewed the role of reading in French in relation to their identity, as well as their views on the role of libraries in supporting their reading needs and practices. The diary activity is underway and is being completed by the participants on their own schedules over a two-month period. The youth are asked to write and reflect about their reading habits each week (with a debriefing session at the end of the time-period). Finally, semi-structured interviews with selected school and public librarians (N=10 to date) will be completed. Among the questions asked of librarians are: What factors inhibit or promote the engagement of French-speaking/learning youth with reading (in French or otherwise)? What outreach strategies could best serve the reading needs of these youth?

Our methodological basis is constructivist grounded theory (Charmaz, 2014), and we approach both the researchers, the youth and other stakeholders involved in the study as creating a shared understanding and interpretation of the phenomenon investigated. While we use sensitizing concepts to structure our inquiry, we move iteratively between data collection and analysis until theoretical saturation has been reached (Birks et al., 2013). The lead researcher is well-versed in community-based research and participatory approaches and is also a native French speaker. Two other team members are also fluent in French. Interactions between the youth and the research team are constant and ongoing and speak to the dedication and potential impact of the research study. Already, the preliminary findings of this study highlight several information needs of bilingual youth and highlight the intersectional and complex nature of those needs. They also highlight the critical role of peers and mentors in unpacking the complexities and uncertainties of the youths' social and emotional lives. The role of the library in these youths' reading practices appears to be rather mixed. A collaborative interpretation lens will add much richness to the study: both during the co-design workshops and the diary activity, we are hoping to have opportunities to reflect with the youth (and other stakeholders) about the significance of reading in/and heritage language loss, (re)acquisition and maintenance. We are hoping to enrich our collaborative interpretive and analytical skills as part of the workshop.

CONCLUSION

This poster outlines a research project currently underway that investigates young people's engagement with reading as members of linguistic and cultural communities in minority contexts. This research investigation promises both theoretical and practical contributions given the dearth of scholarly research in Information Studies on reading in a heritage language as a marker of identity and belonging. Data collection and analysis are in progress, and the timeliness of the Workshop at the ASIS&T Annual Meeting in London, UK is perfect for the needs of the research team. Despite some limitations to this study, including the sample size and the limited focus on Canada, our research will provide both a theoretical model as well as practical implications for local community organizations (schools, libraries, social sector) wishing to deliver successful outreach to youth in their communities.

REFERENCES

- Birks, D. F., Fernandez, W., Levina, N., & Nasirin, S. (2013). Grounded theory method in information systems research: Its nature, diversity and opportunities. *European Journal of Information Systems*, 22(1), 1-8.

- Charmaz, K. (2014). *Constructing grounded theory* (2nd ed.). Los Angeles, CA: Sage.
- Champion, S. (1993). The adolescent quest for meaning through multicultural readings: A case study. *Library Trends*, 41(3), 462+.
- Commissariat aux Services en Langue Française (CSLF). (2018). *Se Projeter, Se Préparer: Rapport 2017-2018*.
- Dali, K. & Hohmann, G. (2022). Preserving the wonder of stories: The role of reflection in reading education in LIS programs. *Journal of Education for Library & Information Science (JELIS)*. Forthcoming.
- Ghaddar, J. & Caidi, N. (2014). Indigenous knowledge in a post-apology era: Steps toward healing and bridge-building. *Bulletin of the Association for Information Science and Technology*, 40(5), June/July issue.
- Grin, F. and Moring, T. (2002). *Final Report: Support for Minority Languages in Europe*. European Centre for Minority Issues, European Commission Document 15.5.2002, Contract 2000-1288/001-001EDU-MLCEV.
- Howard, V. (2011). The importance of pleasure reading in the lives of young teens: Self-identification, self-construction and self-awareness. *Journal of Librarianship and Information Science*, 43(1), 46-55.
- OIF (Organisation Internationale de la Francophonie). (2022). *La langue française dans le monde: 2019-2022*. Gallimard.
- Mahiri, J. (2017). Literacies in the lives of global youth. In B. Street, & S. May (Eds.), *Literacies and language education* (pp. 313-322). Springer International Publishing.
- Nomura, T. & Caidi, N. (2013). "Heritage Language Acquisition and Maintenance: Home Literacy Practices of Japanese-Speaking Families in Canada." *Information Research*, 18(3).
- Shanker, S. (2014). Broader Measures for Success: Social/Emotional Learning. In: *Measuring What Matters, People for Education*. Toronto ON: November 8, 2014.
- Szilagyi, J., & Szecsi, T. (2020). Why and how to maintain the Hungarian language: Hungarian-American families' views on heritage language practices. *Heritage Language Journal*, 17(1), 114-139.
- VanHeerwaarden, N., Ferguson, G, Abi-Jaoude, A., Johnson, A., Hollenberg, E., Chaim, G.,Cleverley, K., Eysenbach, G., Henderson, J., Levinson, A., Robb, J., Sharpe, S., Voineskos, A., & Wiljer, D. (2018). The optimization of an ehealth solution (Thought Spot) with transition-aged youth in postsecondary settings: Participatory design research. *Journal of Medical Internet Research*, 20(3), 1-11.
- Ybarra, M. G. (2022). "Because we have lived it": Chicana/Latina youth multimodal literacies in youth participatory action research. *Reading Research Quarterly*, 57(3), 983-1002.